

Growth of rice in modified microclimates of agroforestry

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In an agroforestry system, radiation received at the ground level is highly variable and consists of alternate patches of light and shade. The level of incident and diffuse radiation affects radiation-use efficiency in crops. Differences in air movement and radiation may also result in spatial variation in temperature and humidity. The importance of soil and floodwater temperatures in the rice crop has been emphasized by Collinson et al (1995). Modifying a crop's microclimate in agroforestry systems is therefore likely to affect crop photosynthesis and evapotranspiration. This study was carried out to measure some components of the microclimate in rice under trees and observe the growth parameters of rice in such modified microclimates.

Cultivar Saket 4 was transplanted at two seedlings hill⁻¹ on 8 Jul 1997 as a lowland puddled rice in an agroforestry system containing 8-y-old *Eucalyptus tereticornis* trees planted in a Nelder fan design (Nelder 1962), and in a control (sole crop) at Pantnagar (India). There were 15 tree-row orientations with each 24° from

the adjacent row (like a wheel with 15 spikes, each making a 24° angle with the adjacent spike), with 10 trees in each row enclosing a total of 15 plots between tree rows. Plots were serially numbered from 1 to 15 in a counterclockwise direction starting from a row oriented to 0° corresponding to the north direction. Trees in each row were at a distance of 2.0, 5.4, 13.5, 17.8, 21.5, 24.6, 27.4, 29.9, 32.2, and 34.4 m, respectively, from the center of the Nelder design, resulting in a constant tree stand of 333 trees ha⁻¹. The trees had an average height of 15.3 m and an average diameter at breast height (DBH) of 16.6 cm. Canopy height, number of panicles and tillers, and grain yields were observed at a selected 1-m row in each plot and in the control. Observations on net radiation (R_n), soil heat flux (G), air temperature (T_a), and floodwater temperature (T_w) were recorded at regular intervals from 0800 to 1700 on 30 Aug, when the crop was at the maximum tillering stage. The instantaneous values of R_n and G were measured with net radiometers and soil heat flux plates (Middleton Instruments,

Australia), and read on portable battery-operated micro-voltmeters (Century Instruments, Chandigarh, India).

The observed growth parameters show a high spatial variation within the experimental area. The percentage of effective panicle-bearing tillers was 96%, 57%, 78%, and 89% in plots 3 (48–72°), 9 (192–216°), and 14 (312–336°) and the control, respectively. These show that the microclimatic conditions were better in plot 3 and poorer in plots 9 and 14 than in the control (see table). Canopy height was greater in plots 3 and 9 than in the control during part of the vegetative growth period (see table), indicating poor light availability at these sites. Grain yields were 6.0, 4.8, 5.4, and 5.1 t ha⁻¹ in plots 3, 9, 14, and the control, respectively.

The R_n and G were greater in the control than in the agroforestry plots (see figure). In addition to variations in cloudiness and changes in the angle of the sun's rays during the day, in agroforestry, tree canopy shading and wind movement through the trees produce fluctuations in radiation received by the rice crop. The

Number of tillers and panicles and canopy height at selected agroforestry sites and control, 1997.

Date of observation	Tillers 1-m row ⁻¹ (no.)				Canopy height (cm)				Panicles 1-m row ⁻¹ (no.)			
	Plot 3	Plot 9	Plot 14	Control	Plot 3	Plot 9	Plot 14	Control	Plot 3	Plot 9	Plot 14	Control
9 Aug	78	57	59	89	70	50	38	57	–	–	–	–
16 Aug	72	64	61	89	88	65	44	64	–	–	–	–
23 Aug	70	66	70	78	105	81	64	74	–	–	–	–
30 Aug	71	64	77	83	105	96	75	76	–	–	–	–
6 Sep	72	65	72	74	112	101	89	90	–	–	–	–
13 Sep	73	65	73	69	112	107	92	98	–	–	–	–
18 Sep	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	18	4	0	7
20 Sep	73	68	73	66	112	107	98	112	51	6	3	10
22 Sep	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	60	17	8	30
25 Sep	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	68	27	17	45
27 Sep	71	72	65	56	112	105	102	120	–	–	–	–
29 Sep	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	67	41	34	50
2 Oct	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	67	41	49	50
9 Oct	71	72	65	56	112	105	102	120	67	41	51	50

Diurnal pattern of net radiation (Rn) and soil heat flux (G) (A), and air temperature (Ta) and floodwater temperature (Tw) (B) in rice at selected agroforestry sites and control, 30 Aug 1997.

magnitude of these fluctuations in Rn, observed on a short-term (second) basis, has a profound effect on crop growth (Knapp and Smith 1990). The development rate of rice is highest at

24–26 °C (Summerfield et al 1992). In this study, air and floodwater temperatures were far greater than this optimum range in the sole crop than in agroforestry (see figure).

Modified microclimates and differences in crop growth parameters can have profound effects on rice yields. The data set presented here is limited because it only indicates possible responses that could be expected under agroforestry. The data, however, suggest options for modifying the crop microclimate by using tree row spacing, orientation, and pruning as management tools in agroforestry. Hence, apart from modifying the crop microclimate by manipulating the canopy architecture through breeding programs, obtaining favorable growth parameters at the same levels of input use under agroforestry conditions can also be a viable management tool.

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Seeding density of rice and its effects on ratoon crop

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We studied the effect of seeding density on the main crop and on a ratoon crop in Santa Catarina State, southern Brazil, located at 28° 56' S in the summer of 1994, 1995, and 1996. The field experiments were conducted in a randomized complete block design with five treatments in 1994 and six in the other 2 years, in four replications at the same site in the 3 years. The soil at the experimental site was Cambicisol Gley. Fertilizer applications for the main crop were 90-40-60 kg NPK ha⁻¹ as urea,

triple superphosphate, and potassium chloride.

An early maturing cultivar (115 d), EPAGRI 106, was seeded with pregerminated seeds in an irrigated lowland rice field during the recommended period (15 October–15 November) at the following treatment rates (kg ha⁻¹): 130 (recommended); 130 + 25% of recommended rate (rr); 130 + 50% rr; 130 + 75% rr; and 130 + 100% rr (260 kg ha⁻¹). In the last 2 years, one more treatment with 100

kg ha⁻¹ was added. The cycle of the main crop (115 d) plus the ratoon (60 d) was 175 d. All data were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) with the F test and linear regression, estimating the response for linear or quadratic effect whenever these effects were significant (F test, $P < 0.05$). The effect of density on yield of the main crop was not significant for any of the 3 years. For the last 2 years, the density × year interaction was not significant (see table).